

Distancing the writing process: A stylometric approach to the session versions of Gie Bogaert's novel *Roosevelt*

Karina van Dalen-Oskam
Huygens Institute, Amsterdam
karina.van.dalen@huygens.knaw.nl

Lamyk Bekius
University of Antwerp, Antwerp
lamyk.bekius@uantwerpen.be

Introduction

What insights can we gain by applying text analysis methods from computational literary studies (CLS) to hundreds of versions of a novel-in-progress? We were able to explore this question because the Flemish author Gie Bogaert logged the writing process of his tenth novel *Roosevelt* (2016), using the keystroke logger Inputlog (Leijten and Van Waes 2013). In cognitive writing process research, keystroke logging has often been deployed for research on short writing processes within educational and corporate contexts, but not often to study the long-term literary writing processes. To fill this gap, the team behind Inputlog – Mariëlle Leijten and Luuk Van Waes – approached Bogaert with the question if he was willing to log the writing process of his next novel. Bogaert agreed and logged the writing process of *Roosevelt* from July 2013 to December 2015, during 447 writing sessions (of which 422 were dedicated to the actual writing of the novel). At the start and end of each writing session, Inputlog automatically saves the Word document (the ‘session versions’) and in the meantime it records every keystroke and mouse movement along with a timestamp. The 422 writing sessions resulted in 453 Word documents as well as 277 hours, 14 minutes and 22 seconds of keystroke logging data.¹ Before Bogaert started this digital part of his writing process, he prepared the structure and content of the novel in a paper notebook consisting of over 100 pages. The writing process has been studied from a text genetic perspective by Lamyk Bekius as part of the research project ‘Track Changes: Textual scholarship and the challenge of digital literary writing’ (2018-2024), funded by the Dutch Research Council (NWO) (see Bekius 2021; 2023).

In this presentation, we present the results of our exploratory stylometric study of the different versions of the novel. The Principal Components Analysis (PCA) and Burrows’ Delta Distance, as implemented in the Stylo Package for R (Eder et al. 2016), are the methods central to our study of the development of *Roosevelt* during the writing process. We compare the results of the stylometric analysis with those of the text genetic study to explore whether the computational approach can provide knowledge about Bogaert’s creative writing process. In particular, we investigate whether stylometric analysis can provide insights into writing phases and the development of character voices.

Aims

Roosevelt is a kaleidoscopic city novel with a public square – the Franklin Roosevelt Square in Antwerp, Belgium – as its main narrator. In the first chapter, Franklin announces that he will give the word to a couple of people who all have their occupations on the square that day. As

¹ Incidentally, the start Word document of a writing session is not the same as the end document of the previous session, which is why there are more Word documents than sessions.

a result, the novel consists of 62 short sections, all narrated in the first person by one of thirteen different characters. This specific structure of the novel informs our study in two ways. Firstly, Bekius (2023) has shown that Bogaert’s writing process for *Roosevelt* was a rather cyclical one: for each overarching chapter he repeatedly went through a cycle of first retyping his notes from his notebook for all the character sections in that chapter and adding additional notes, then textualising these notes one character section at a time, and mostly ending with making revisions to the sections within the chapter (see Fig. 1). We wanted to explore whether this cyclical process can also be observed in the stylometric visualisation.

Second, research by Hoover (2014; 2017), Larry L. Stewart (2003), Karina van Dalen-Oskam (2014), Lisa Pearl, Kristine Lu, and Anousheh Haghighi (2017), and Daniil Skorinkin and Boris Orekhov (2023), among others, has shown that stylometry can be helpful in analysing differences between character or narrator voices. We therefore sought to investigate whether differences in style can be found between the character voices in *Roosevelt* and how these voices were shaped during the writing process: were the distinct voices already implemented from the beginning of the writing process or did their distinctiveness only emerge in later versions of the novel?

Figure 1: Macro-genetic visualisation of the sections Bogaert worked on in session 176–231. Sessions 226–228, indicated with black rectangle, show that Bogaert worked on multiple character sections, in those session he usually included notes.²

Results: writing phases

We found that stylometric analysis did yield some insights into Bogaert’s writing phases. One of our initial analyses, a cluster analysis (Classic Delta Distance) of the session versions of

² See for the complete macro-genetic visualisation: <https://nanogenesis-digital.github.io/html/macro-roosevelt.html>

every tenth session including the published version of the novel (Fig. 2), present two main clusters: one with session versions 010-180 and the other with session version 190 and higher.

Figure 2: Cluster analysis (Classic Delta Distance) of the session versions of every tenth session including the published version of the novel, 1000 most frequent words.

A close reading of the session versions leads to the hypothesis that the break between session 180 and 190 could be explained by a large increase of text as well as by a decrease in the ratio of notes to fully developed text. Further analyses also show some effect of the notes on the clusters. This was particularly evident in the middle part of the writing process, where there was a clear division between sessions in which Bogaert added notes and sessions in which he textualised these notes. For example, session versions related to sessions in which he added notes showed an increase in the relative frequency of the word ‘over’ [‘about’]. This word is a quite characteristic word for notes that appear in the Atoma notebook and which were sometimes literally retyped into the Word document. For example, Bogaert added the note we highlighted in yellow in Figure 3 in session 226 to the section of Janine. For the middle part of the writing process, the session versions that showed an increase in the word ‘over’ were part of a different cluster than the previous session version. Nevertheless, the phases identified on the basis of macrogenetic visualisation and stylometric analysis do not fully coincide, and the effect of Bogaert’s particular phases ceases to exist from the moment the

fully developed text takes precedence over the note-like text. The phases thus seem to provide only a partial explanation for the differences between the session versions hinted at by the stylometric analysis.

Figure 3: One of the notes with the word 'over' in the Atoma notebook that Bogaert copied into the Word document (yellow highlighting added for clarity by ourselves): 'Over schulden en hoe zij en Leo (nog onschuldig hier) daarmee proberen om te gaan' ['About debt and how she and Leo (still innocent here) are trying to deal with it']

Figure 4: Principal components analysis (correlation matrix) of the sessions of each narrator in which

the texts first reached 1000, 1500, and 2000 tokens, and the published version of the nine narrators with more than 2000 tokens in the published version of the novel, 100 most frequent words.

Results: character voices

For the character voices, we found that a stylometric analysis comparing the texts of the nine narrators with more than 2000 tokens in the published version of the novel contributes to an informed depiction of how these voices unfolded during the writing process. We first created a corpus consisting of one text file for each writing session per narrator. This corpus consists of 4,056 files. To overcome the problem of having too many files, we selected four files for each narrator: the session where the text first reached 1000, 1500, and 2000 tokens, and the published version. In the PCA (Fig. 4) we can observe that the four text versions of most of the narrators end up close together, suggesting that Bogaert did not significantly alter their voice or style during the writing process. Larger differences can be observed only for the versions of Faraaz. This could indicate that it took Bogaert more effort to linguistically shape the voice of this narrator than for the others. A close reading of the versions suggest that a reason for this can be found in Bogaert's process of writing the sections of Faraaz. Relatively early in the writing process, the text of Faraaz reached a high number of tokens, but this text consisted mainly of a description of an Iranian wedding ceremony written in a rather impersonal, informative style. Only later in the writing process, Faraaz's 'own' character voice outweighed the descriptive text: after session 313 (which is the last session version included in Figure 3 before the published version), two of the five sections of Faraaz still needed to be elaborated with text from Faraaz's own perspective. Regarding differences in narrator voices, relative differences between the narrators can be observed and different measurements repeatedly show the same division into two groups of characters. However, it lies beyond the scope of this exploratory study to investigate this further, through, for example, keyword analysis as done by Culpeper (2014a, 2014b), and n-gram analysis and keyword analysis as developed by Šeļa et al. (2023). Nevertheless, we can conclude that stylometric analysis can lead to more insight into the creative writing process. Having a large number of versions of a text as research data can thus lead to promising avenues in computational stylometry.

References

- Bekius, Lamyk. *'Behind the Screens'. The Use of Keystroke Logging for Genetic Criticism Applied to Born-Digital Works of Literature*, University of Amsterdam and University of Antwerp, 2023, PhD Dissertation.
- Bekius, Lamyk. De geboorte van een plein: De analoge en digitale tekstgenese van het incipit in Gie Bogaerts roman Roosevelt. *Tijdschrift voor Nederlandse Taal- en Letterkunde*, vol. 137, no. 2, Jan. 2021, pp. 122–49, <https://doi.org/10.5117/TNTL2021.2.002.BEKI>.
- Bogaert, Gie. *Roosevelt*. Amsterdam/Antwerpen, De Bezige Bij, 2016.
- Culpeper, Jonathan (2014a). Keywords and characterization. An analysis of six characters in Romeo and Juliet. *Digital literary studies. Corpus approaches to poetry, prose, and drama*. Edited by David L. Hoover, Jonathan Culpeper, and Kieran O'Halloran, London and New York: Routledge, 2014, pp. 9-34.
- Culpeper, Jonathan (2014b). Developing keyness and characterization. Annotation. *Digital literary studies. Corpus approaches to poetry, prose, and drama*. Edited by David L. Hoover,

- Jonathan Culpeper, and Kieran O'Halloran, London and New York: Routledge, 2014, pp. 35-63.
- Eder, Maciej, Mike Kestemont, and Jan Rybicki. Stylometry with R: A package for computational text analysis. *The R Journal*, vol. 8, no. 1, 2016, pp. 1–15, <https://journal.r-project.org/articles/RJ-2016-007/>.
- Hoover, David L. *The Moonstone and The Coquette*. Narrative and epistolary style. *Digital literary studies. Corpus approaches to poetry, prose, and drama*. Edited by David L. Hoover, Jonathan Culpeper, and Kieran O'Halloran, London and New York: Routledge, 2014, pp. 64-89.
- Hoover, David L. The microanalysis of style variation. *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities*, vol. 32, suppl. 2, 2017, pp. ii17–ii30, <https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/fqx022>.
- Leijten, Mariëlle, and Luuk Van Waes. Keystroke Logging in Writing Research: Using Inputlog to Analyze and Visualize Writing Processes. *Written Communication*, vol. 30, no. 3, 2013, pp. 358–92, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0741088313491692>.
- Pearl, Lisa, Kristine Lu, Anousheh Haghighi. The character in the letter: Epistolary attribution in Samuel Richardson's *Clarissa*. *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities*, vol. 32, no. 2, 2017, pp. 355–376, <https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/fqw007>.
- Šeĵa, Artjoms, et al. From stage to page: language independent bootstrap measures of distinctiveness in fictional speech. 2023, [preprint] *arXiv:2301.05659v1 [cs.CL]*, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2301.05659>.
- Skorinkin, Daniil, and Boris Orekhov. Hacking stylometry with multiple voices: Imaginary writers can override authorial signal in Delta. *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities*, vol. 38, no. 3, 2023, pp. 1247–1266, <https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/fqad012>.
- Stewart, Larry L. Charles Brockden Brown: Quantitative Analysis and Literary Interpretation. *Literary and Linguistic Computing*, vol. 18, no. 2, 2003, pp. 129–138, <https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/18.2.129>.
- Van Dalen-Oskam, Karina. Epistolary voices. The case of Elisabeth Wolff and Agatha Deken. *Literary and Linguistic Computing*, vol. 29, no. 3, 2014, pp. 443–451, <https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/fqu023>.